

This contribution is part of the Erasmus+ Project
Eurhythmics in Education and Artistic Practice (EEAP)

Captured mo(ve)ments - plastique animée exhibition

Barbara Dutkiewicz

The exhibition *Captured mo(ve)ments* was prepared in Katowice in 2023 by Barbara Dutkiewicz. It is an outcome of the LTT 21-25.03.2022 weekly workshop. The creative process presented during the exhibition documents the choreographic work according to the principles of *plastique animée*. *Plastique animée* is a specific way of an artistic activity which combines music and movement where the body moving in space builds an artistic statement on stage.

This work, excluding figures, is licensed under CC BY 4.0.

ISBN 978-83-963687-4-4

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7789474>

Captured mo(ve)ments - plastique animée exhibition

Barbara Dutkiewicz

Plastique animée is a specific way of an artistic activity which combines music and movement where the body moving in space builds an artistic statement on stage. Elusiveness of the shapes and structure of space setting created by the body movement is usually perceived, decoded and memorized by the recipient. This time the transitory moments were caught by the eye of the camera.

Photos presented at the exhibition were taken by Robert Rogucki in the Theater Hall of The Karol Szymanowski Academy of Music in Katowice, Poland during rehearsals (1, 9, 17) and the final concert. The music choreography to Henryk Mikołaj Górecki's composition *'Kleines Requiem für eine Polka op. 66'* for piano and 13 instruments in four parts was created by Barbara Dutkiewicz and Iga Eckert during the workshop week LTT (Learning Teaching Training) 21-25.03.2022. It was a part of the international project Eurhythmics in Education and Artistic Practice implemented thanks to the program Erasmus+ (module 'Plastique animée - tradition and contemporary performing'). The module ended with the 'Concert of Plastique Animée and improvisation', where the choreography has its premiere. The participants were students from Universität für Musik und darstellende Kunst Wien, Austria and students from the eurhythmics specialty at The Department of Music Education and Eurhythmics in AM Katowice.

From the left: Iga Eckert, Barbara Dutkiewicz and workshop participants

In the photos created by Mr Rogucki we can see selected choreographic scenes performed by the following Austrian and Polish students: Theresa Kanak, Caterina Voegel, Emilia Forck, Antonia Luksch, Hanna Spannagl, Zurisadai Rivas, Mohadese Siasar, Sabrina Kuenig, Marta Ansone, Nicola Hudelmayer, Paulina Figaszewska, Blanka Moryc, Natalia Kidoń, Patrycja Widlarz, Marianna Siptarova, Oliwia Skrzypczak, Patrycja Wywrocka, Ewelina Gałysa, Natalia Janikowska, Maria Flig, Marta Jarzyna, Karolina Lisowska, Martyna Wojsyk.

Concert performers and eurhythmics teachers

It is a photographic documentation of the project and it completes two publications:

1. *Plastique animée - embodied music moving in space* (2023), ISBN 978-83-963687-2-0 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7789399>
2. *Choreography of music. Process of creation according to the principles of plastique animée on the example of music by Henryk Mikołaj Górecki 'Kleines Requiem für eine Polka op. 66', choreography created by Barbara Dutkiewicz and Iga Eckert* (2023), ISBN 978-83-963687-3-7 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7789711>

Below in the description the quotations from the website of the Polish Center for Music Information¹ www.polmic.pl were used.

¹ https://www.polmic.pl/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=877:tvp-kultura-henryk-mikoaj-gorecki-mae-requiem-dla-pewnej-polki-op-66-na-fortepian-i-13-instrumentow-1993-premiera-tvp-kultura-17-listopada-2010-godz-2250&Itemid=50&lang=pl

Captured mo(ve)ments

Part One - *Tranquillo*

„Tranquillo opens with the ominous sound of bells and a persistently recurring figure in the piano part with empty fifths in the background. The tender melodic thread in muted dynamics is then developed by the strings, only to repeat the material in a moment with the strength of a desperate scream’ - www.polmic.pl

Part Two - *Allegro impetuoso-marcatisimo*

*'The expressively intense second movement, *Allegro impetuoso-marcatisimo*, includes a broad consonance of the piano with prominent thirds, so characteristic of Górecki, and provocative motifs of the other instruments. The link is crowned by the touching singing of the clarinet and a subtle coda of the strings' - www.polmic.pl*

Part Three - *Allegro-deciso assai*

'In Allegro-deciso assai reflects Górecki's penchant for simple, folk music accompanying free play. When the dizzying pace of the dance stops, the mood of the last bars of the second movement returns' - www.polmic.pl

Part Four - Adagio-cantabiles

'Mood of the last bars of the second movement returns which determines the final Adagio-cantabiles, with piano chords fading into nothingness' - www.polmic.pl

'*Captured mo(ve)ments - plastique animée exhibition*' is a combination of sound, body movement and visual elements rooted in music composition, choreography and photo graphics. These three separate arts complement and intertwine one other.

Below you will find some information about them.

,'*Kleines Requiem für eine Polka*' [by Henryk Mikołaj Górecki] was commissioned in 1993 by the Holland Festival. The recipient of the dedication is the Schönberg Ensemble, [performed] the composition in Krakow. The premiere in June 1993 in Amsterdam was conducted by Reinbert de Leeuw' - www.polmic.pl

Music choreography by Barbara Dutkiewicz and Iga Eckert premiered at The Karol Szymanowski Academy of Music in Katowice, Poland 2022.

Photos by Robert Rogucki

ISBN 978-83-963687-4-4

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7789474>

Vita

Barbara Dutkiewicz (PhD, hab.) works as an Associate Professor at The Karol Szymanowski Academy of Music in Katowice, Poland where she teaches: Eurhythmics, Methodology of Eurhythmics Teaching, Plastique animée - Movement Choreography of Music, Movement Techniques, Piano Improvisation in Eurhythmics Method.

She is the author of over 70 choreographies performed e.g. in Poland (at The Krzysztof Penderecki European Center for Music in Luśławice; Polish National Radio Symphony Orchestra in Katowice, The Świętokrzyska Philharmonic, the Radio Katowice Concert Studio, The Silesian Theatre in Katowice, The Korez Theatre in Katowice, The Rozrywka Theatre in Chorzów and at the Music Academies in Katowice, Łódź, Poznań, Gdańsk) and abroad in the Netherlands, Germany, Austria, the Czech Republic, Ukraine and USA.

She often leads workshops and master classes in Europe, Asia and America. She is the author of over 20 articles published in Polish and foreign journals. As post-doctoral theses (habilitation) she published a book entitled: '*Polistylistics or Discourse with the Past - Choreography of Music in the Light of Postmodernism on the Basis of Chosen Musical Works*' (2012). She was awarded the first prize at the First European Eurhythmics Competition in Trossingen, Germany in 1994.

See more <http://www.barbaradutkiewicz.pl/index.php/en>

<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-3888-0325>

Contact: b.dutkiewicz@am.katowice.pl

Iga Eckert, MA. Masters in both Eurhythmics and Conducting of vocal and vocal-instrumental ensembles (in the conducting class of PhD Szymon Bywalec; laureate of the Promotion of Young Culture Creators, Prize of Katowice City (2007, 2009). Multiple workshops in the range of musical movement expression, improvisation, movement interpretation, voice emission and music-making complete her pedagogical activity. She participated in many courses and workshops in the field of dance, eurhythmics, solfeggio, voice emission and general music education, both in Poland and abroad, including: the Emil Jaques-Dalcroze Institute in Geneva, the Zoltan Kodaly Institute in Kecskemet, Vienna University of Music and Performing Arts or LAVAL University in Quebec. Since 2010, she has been working for the Wojciech Kilar State Music Schools in Katowice (eurhythmics, ear training). She teaches piano improvisation as well as plastique animee and movement expression at the Academy of Music in Katowice. In 2019, she created the organizing committee of The 4th International Conference of Dalcroze Studies in Katowice. She is the conductor of the children's choir at the State Primary Music School in Katowice and the Largo choir of the Evangelical-Augsburg parish in Świętochłowice.

Her artistic activity is complemented by compositions for over 20 performances (an honorable distinction at the 30th National Festival of Puppet Theaters) and radio plays. She cooperates with institutional theaters as well as private, informal artistic groups. She is a co-founder of the Poddańczy Theater association where, apart from artistic challenges, she is involved in social campaigns.

<https://orcid.org/0009-0004-0622-5101>

ISBN 978-83-963687-4-4

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7789474>

Universität der Künste Berlin